

Notes and Narratives: Using Music to Tune ESL Brains in Canada's Classrooms

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Introduction

In the Canadian educational system, various methods for teaching English as a Second Language (ESL) have been implemented to support the growing number of immigrant and international students. These methods often emphasize practical language skills for social, academic, and professional contexts. Approaches to ESL education include scaffolded academic programs (Lesaux & Geva, 2006), culturally responsive teaching (Gay, 2010), collaborative or co-teaching models (Tomlinson, 2001), and technology-enhanced learning (Blin, 2016). Despite these varied approaches, ESL students face several challenges that hinder language acquisition and integration. Many students experience cognitive overload due to the dual demand of learning English while keeping up with academic content, which can slow their progress. Social and emotional challenges and sociocultural elements also impact learning, as students may feel isolated or anxious, hindering their language practice and classroom engagement (Roessingh, 2018).

Derwing and Munro (2015) highlight how linguistic barriers, such as challenges in phonological production and accent adaptation, create significant obstacles in acquiring fluency and comprehension in English. Many ESL learners struggle with pronunciation and phonology, which affects their intelligibility and overall communicative competence (Derwing & Munro, 2015). Additionally, syntax and vocabulary acquisition pose challenges for ESL learners, as English requires an understanding of complex grammatical structures and a broad lexicon (Gass

& Selinker, 2018). Some research evidence suggests that certain aspects of music training may support second language (L2) learning by enhancing cognitive and auditory processing skills that overlap music and language acquisition (Tierney & Kraus, 2014). This paper will review the extant research regarding potential connections between musical training and L2 learning in order to determine what if any potential benefits ESL learners may gain from including music training as a component of their practice.

Shared Resources Between Language and Music Learning

The OPERA hypothesis, proposed by Patel (2011), provides a compelling framework for understanding the potential cognitive and neural benefits of music training for language processing. Patel's hypothesis centers around the concept of "resource-sharing" in the brain: since music training enhances abilities in pitch perception, rhythm, and auditory memory, such training may improve analogous skills essential for language acquisition, such as phonological awareness and syntactic processing. According to this hypothesis, music training enhances the precision of auditory processing through the activation of overlapping brain networks used for both music and language. Patel suggests that music training not only stimulates these shared auditory regions but does so in a way that exceeds the demands of ordinary speech, thereby fostering neural plasticity that benefits speech and language skills (Patel, 2011; Strait & Kraus, 2011). The acronym OPERA stands for five key conditions that contribute to this neural enhancement: (a) Overlap - music and language processing share neural regions, particularly for sound features like pitch and rhythm; (b) Precision - music demands higher auditory precision than typical language use, engaging these networks more intensely; (c) Emotion - music often evokes strong emotions, increasing engagement and retention; (d) Repetition - musical practice

involves repeated exposure, which strengthens the neural pathways involved; and (e) Attention - focused attention in music training activates these networks, reinforcing neural connections.

These conditions highlight the synergistic effect of music training on auditory perception and its potential application to second language acquisition (Patel, 2011; Koelsch, 2011).

For example, language acquisition activates regions of the brain associated with speech production and comprehension, such as Broca's and Wernicke's areas (Friederici, 2011). Broca's area is also activated during music training, particularly in tasks involving musical syntax and structure (Patel 2008), while Wernicke's area is involved in processing musical elements such as pitch and melody, linking it to linguistic processing (Peretz & Coltheart, 2003). The auditory cortex is crucial to both language acquisition and music learning. This region of the brain is responsible for processing sound features such as pitch, rhythm, and phonemes, enabling the discrimination of speech sounds in language and fine-grained auditory perception in music, essential for recognizing melodies and harmonies (Kuhl, 2004; Zatorre et al., 2007). The basal ganglia, facilitate motor coordination and timing, playing a central role in rhythm production and processing for both speech and music. These structures also support the procedural learning of language grammar and musical patterns, reinforcing habitual practices (Kotz et al., 2009).

Learning a new language and learning music both involve complex processes of neuroplasticity, memory, and sensory integration. Neuroplasticity, also known as brain plasticity, is the brain's innate ability to reorganize itself by forming new neural connections in response to learning, environmental changes, or even injury. This phenomenon reflects the brain's adaptability, allowing it to modify its structural and functional networks to optimize performance in response to stimuli (Kolb & Gibb, 2011). Changes in the brain occur within structural and

functional processes that refer to distinct types of neuroplastic adaptations. Structural changes are physical alterations in brain anatomy, such as changes in gray matter volume, white matter connectivity, or the density of specific brain regions (Zatorre, Fields, & Johansen-Berg, 2012). Functional changes, on the other hand, involve modifications in the way brain areas activate and interact during tasks, often resulting in increased efficiency or different neural activation patterns within and between brain regions (Pascual-Leone et al., 2005). Functional changes are typically seen in alterations to neural networks and the recruitment of additional or fewer areas for specific tasks, depending on the individual's level of expertise or adaptation (Patel, 2011). In music training, functional changes include increased activation and synchronization in auditory processing areas, motor regions, and prefrontal cortical areas, reflecting enhanced skills in auditory discrimination, memory, and cognitive control (Schlaug et al., 2003).

In the context of cognitive skill-building, neuroplasticity supports various adaptations in response to music and language learning domains with known overlapping processes in auditory and cognitive processing areas of the brain (Barrett et al., 2021). This plasticity underscores how the brain can reorganize itself to support language learning, a process that is cognitively demanding and requires heightened auditory discrimination and memory functions (Patel, 2011). The neuroplastic effects of music training are distinct from other types of learning due to the complex and multimodal nature of music itself, which involves auditory, motor, cognitive, and emotional components (Herholz & Zatorre, 2012). Neuroplasticity allows these regions to adapt, especially in early sensitive periods, enhancing proficiency (Kolb & Gibb, 2011; Moreno et al., 2013).

Memory

Research (e.g., Kraus & Chandrasekaran, 2010) also suggests that music training enhances various cognitive abilities, including working memory, executive function, and auditory attention. These enhanced cognitive skills may significantly influence the ease with which learners acquire a second language. Vocabulary acquisition and semantic memory formation are associated with the hippocampus, a region that also plays a multifaceted role in music learning by supporting memory processes, spatial-temporal reasoning, and emotional engagement. The hippocampus is central to encoding and retrieving declarative and episodic memories, enabling musicians to recall melodies, lyrics, and theoretical knowledge (Altenmüller & Schlaug, 2015). Additionally, the hippocampus facilitates pattern recognition and spatial organization, crucial for interpreting musical notation and coordinating rhythms (Herholz & Zatorre, 2012).

Prior research (e.g., Hamann, 2001; Koelsch et al., 2009) has indicated that emotional arousal facilitates the consolidation of information in memory, a process supported by the amygdala and hippocampus, which work together to prioritize emotionally significant events. This mechanism strengthens emotionally significant information for long-term storage (McGaugh, 2004; Kensinger & Corkin, 2004). Music provides a rich contextual and emotional environment that can facilitate episodic memory encoding, with studies showing improved retrieval when emotional or multisensory contexts are integrated during encoding (Hamann, 2001; Hupbach et al., 2008). Neuroimaging evidence also indicates that the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) and other regions associated with organizational and semantic memory encoding are more active in these enriched contexts, particularly when music is involved as a mnemonic device (Blumenfeld & Ranganath, 2007; Innocenti et al., 2010).

This enhancement in memory processing extends to verbal memory, suggesting that music training may improve memory for both musical and non-musical information, potentially offering significant implications for language learning (Patel, 2011). Pastuszek-Lipińska (2008) provided an insightful exploration of the effects of music on L2 and ESL learning, with a particular focus on vocabulary acquisition. The study indicated that music, through its rhythmic and melodic properties, could aid in encoding and retrieval of words, thus enhancing learners' vocabulary retention. Pastuszek-Lipińska's findings suggested that music acts as a dual stimulus, engaging both auditory and motor pathways, which strengthen learners' ability to process and recall new vocabulary over time. One of the central claims in the study was that music's repetitive nature provides learners with a more immersive environment for language acquisition. The study highlighted that songs with lyrics facilitated a multisensory experience, making language input more engaging and memorable. Pastuszek-Lipińska found that music enhances the emotional resonance of vocabulary, making it more likely to be retained in long-term memory. These findings align with language acquisition theories such as Krashen's Input Hypothesis (Krashen, 1982), which suggests that learners acquire language more effectively when the input is emotionally engaging.

Moreno et al. (2009) used behavioral experiments combined with event-related potential (ERP) measures to investigate the effects of music training on auditory and memory processes. Participants in the study underwent tasks requiring auditory discrimination and memory recall while their neural activity was monitored. The study analyzed how musical training influenced the N400 component, which is associated with semantic and auditory processing, demonstrating transfer effects to language tasks. The study concluded that such effects were not only specific to music but may also have transfer effects on other skills, such as language, by enhancing auditory

discrimination and memory processes (Moreno et al., 2009). Moreover, repeated musical training facilitates a process known as perceptual tuning, wherein the brain becomes more sensitive to specific auditory stimuli, such as pitch and rhythm. This heightened sensitivity subsequently strengthens neural networks in motor regions and prefrontal areas, which are essential for memory, attention, and executive function (Kraus & Chandrasekaran, 2010).

Phonological Awareness

Together, phonological awareness, prosody, intonation, and stress are essential for fluent comprehension and natural-sounding speech in English, especially for L2 learners working on grasping the subtleties of spoken language. These subtleties contribute to the rhythm, prominence, and emotional tone of speech (Levis, 2018; Prieto & Roseano, 2010). Phonological awareness is defined as the "ability to detect and manipulate the sound structure of language, separate from its meaning" (Anthony & Francis, 2005). Research has demonstrated that music training, particularly involving rhythm and pitch, can enhance phonological awareness by engaging overlapping neural pathways used in both music and language processing (Patel, 2012; Tierney & Kraus, 2013). For example, Pastuszek-Lipinska (2008) explored how shared neural pathways between music and language processing might facilitate L2 learning. Native Polish-speaking participants were divided into two groups designated as (a) musicians (those with at least eight years of formal music training) and (b) non-musicians (those without at least eight years of formal music training). Participants were tasked with imitating sentences in six languages (English, French, Italian, Spanish, Japanese, and Belgian Dutch), synthesized using text-to-speech software to ensure consistent stimuli. The speech samples were analyzed both impressionistically and statistically. A web-based test allowed native speakers to rate the fluency

and accuracy of the participants' productions on a visual analog scale. Results indicated that musical training could enhance phonetic, syntactic, and lexical aspects of language learning, largely due to improvements in auditory discrimination, memory, and attention. Participants in the musician group consistently outperformed those in the non-musician group in imitating sentences and reproducing phonological features accurately across all tested languages. Musicians' productions were rated as more native-like, reflecting their superior phonological memory and auditory processing abilities, facilitating better handling of linguistic elements such as phonemes, syntax, and intonation. The researcher posited that pitch, rhythm, and tonal skills cultivated through music training may support language processing, particularly in children, as younger brains exhibit higher levels of neuroplasticity.

Fernandez de Canete, Pineda, and Waddell (2022) explored the integration of music into language instruction through the *Music as a Medium of Instruction* (MMI) approach, which emphasizes music's potential to support language development by enhancing phonological awareness and auditory processing. The researchers compared the effectiveness of the MMI approach with a gamified English learning approach among 22 Spanish children. Participants were divided based on prior music training experience. Results showed significant benefits of the MMI approach for oral production and listening comprehension, particularly among students with prior musical training.

Milovanov et al. (2010) explored the influence of musical aptitude on L2 learners' phonological awareness. To test this relationship, the authors used a series of linguistic tasks involving both sound discrimination and sound reproduction. The discrimination task required participants to identify differences in sounds from unfamiliar languages (Arabic and Serbian),

while the productive task required them to listen to and reproduce those sounds. Participants' musical aptitude was measured using the Advanced Measures of Music Audiation (AMMA), which evaluates rhythmic and melodic discrimination abilities. The results demonstrated that individuals with higher musical aptitude performed significantly better in distinguishing and reproducing phonetic elements, suggesting that musical aptitude enhances phonological awareness, particularly in the auditory processing and sound discrimination areas, which are crucial for language acquisition.

Zhang, Baills, and Prieto (2022) further observed that music-based instruction improved adolescent ESL learners' pronunciation and vocabulary skills in Chinese speakers. The study found that incorporating singing into language lessons aided phonetic development by increasing learners' exposure to authentic pronunciation in a rhythmically engaging way. This method was shown to boost retention and recall of new vocabulary as well, suggesting that song-based learning could serve as a strong complement to traditional language instruction for improving English phonological skills (Zhang et al., 2022).

The impact of rhythm-based music training on phonological awareness is also well-supported by research, indicating that rhythm perception is critical for auditory processing in both language and music learning. For example, Vuust and Witek (2014) examined rhythm processing in musicians and its implications for language acquisition. Their research underscored the fact that rhythm is foundational in both music and language, with shared reliance on temporal precision and sequential processing. The researchers found that musicians with rhythm training demonstrated superior phonological awareness and temporal alignment in language tasks. This cross-domain skill transfer suggests that rhythm training in music may foster language

acquisition by enhancing timing and sequencing abilities critical for spoken language comprehension.

Tierney and Kraus (2013) explored how the perception of rhythm and pitch in music may be linked to grammatical understanding and language production. The researchers utilized behavioral assessments that measured participants' abilities to process rhythm and pitch in musical contexts. These tests were then correlated with measures of linguistic abilities, including interpreting prosodic features of language such as intonation and stress patterns, grammatical understanding, and language production tasks. The findings suggested that rhythm-based interventions enhanced temporal processing abilities, a core component for distinguishing phonetic contrasts that are challenging for L2 learners. In addition, findings also indicated that musical training improved neural timing, reducing the cognitive load required for phonemic discrimination, and leading to greater accuracy in pronunciation and listening comprehension for ESL learners. Musical training was associated with enhanced timing precision in the brainstem, which was reflected in improved neural discrimination of phonemes. This suggests that musical training may optimize auditory processing mechanisms, thereby reducing the cognitive effort required for tasks such as phonemic discrimination. Such findings have been corroborated by neuroimaging studies that reveal structural changes in auditory and motor regions associated with music training, indicating that rhythm exercises stimulate auditory pathways that are also activated during language tasks (Artiktay, 2024; Strait & Kraus, 2021).

Pastuszek-Lipińska (2008) draws on research showing that the rhythmic patterns found in music mirror those in language, making it easier for learners to internalize grammatical structures. This connection between musical rhythm and syntactic processing is also supported by studies from Maess and Koelsch (2001), who employed EEG techniques to examine brain

responses when participants heard unexpected musical chords within harmonic sequences. These unexpected chords elicited a specific brain response known as the early right anterior negativity (ERAN), which occurs similarly in response to syntactic irregularities in language. This finding suggests that the brain processes musical syntax—rules governing how notes and chords are organized—through mechanisms that partially overlap with those used in language syntax processing. Such overlap between music and language processing may indicate shared neural resources in the brain's frontal areas, particularly in the inferior frontal gyrus and Broca's area, which are known for their role in language syntax. Maess and Koelsch's findings imply that music training, which enhances sensitivity to musical syntax, could potentially benefit syntactic processing in language as well (Maess & Koelsch, 2001). Subsequent research expanded on these findings, confirming the involvement of similar brain regions in syntactic processing across both domains (Koelsch et al., 2005; Patel, 2008).

Prosody refers to the rhythm, stress, and intonation patterns of speech that help convey meaning and emotion in spoken language (Gandour et al., 1994). Prosody plays a role in phonological awareness, as sensitivity to rhythmic patterns can enhance early reading skills and vocabulary acquisition by aiding in segmenting words and sounds within spoken language (Wood, 2006). A simple example of prosody is how one might say "Oh, really?" in different situations. One might encounter this phrase spoken with a rising tone and enthusiasm, showing surprise or excitement. Or one might encounter the phrase spoken with a flat, disinterested tone showing indifference or boredom. Intonation refers to the variation in pitch that occurs across speech, playing a key role in the communication of meaning, emotion, and intent. It includes the rising and falling of pitch during speech, which can differentiate between types of sentences (e.g., statements versus questions), convey emotions, or indicate the structure of an utterance

(Ladd, 2008). Intonation helps focus the listener's attention on important parts of a message and organizes speech into units that are easier to process and remember (Wells, 2006). In language acquisition, intonation patterns support the comprehension of longer, complex sentences by providing auditory signals that clarify meaning and speaker intent. When asking a question like, "Are you coming to the party?" the pitch usually rises at the end, signaling it is a question. This rising intonation distinguishes questions from statements, helping listeners understand the speaker's intent. Similarly, a sentence like "That was amazing!" may have a higher, varied pitch to convey excitement, while "It's okay" might have a flat pitch to show indifference (Wells, 2006). Stress patterns refer to the arrangement of syllables in words and sentences based on their relative emphasis or prominence. Stressed syllables are pronounced with greater force, higher pitch, or longer duration, while unstressed syllables are weaker or quieter. Sentence stress highlights keywords for emphasis in speech (Roach, 2009). Understanding these patterns is essential for intelligibility and naturalness in communication. In English, certain syllables within words are emphasized more than others. For example, when the word 'record' is used as a noun (e.g., a music record), the stress falls on the first syllable. However, when the word is used as a verb (e.g., to record a video), the stress is on the second syllable. Stress patterns help distinguish word meanings and enhance comprehension, especially when context doesn't clarify word function.

Patel (2012) described how musical pitch processing and linguistic pitch, or prosody, share overlapping neural mechanisms. His research findings indicated that pitch sensitivity developed through music training enhanced the understanding of emotional cues, intonation, and emphasis in language (Patel, 2008). The researcher explained that musical pitch processing trains the brain in ways that overlap with linguistic pitch processing, which is essential for decoding the

prosody of language, created by elements such as stress, intonation, and emotional tone. By developing a heightened sensitivity to pitch through music training, ESL learners may better understand emotional cues, question intonation, and word emphasis in language, enhancing their communicative competence. Moreno et al. (2009) conducted a study on children to test whether music training could improve their ability to perceive speech in noisy environments. Using pre- and post-assessments of speech perception, the researchers found that children who underwent music training had increased accuracy in identifying speech sounds within background noise, a skill crucial for language comprehension in real-world settings. The researchers suggested that music training may enhance the auditory system's robustness and sensitivity, making it easier to discern linguistic information in challenging listening conditions.

Research by Tierney and Kraus (2013) explored the auditory brainstem's role in processing pitch contours, a common feature in both music and language. The researchers used neural recordings to observe how well individuals could track pitch changes, finding that music training was linked to a more finely tuned pitch perception mechanism in the auditory brainstem. Since pitch perception is essential for understanding intonation, tone, and stress in spoken language, the authors suggested that musical training might enhance one's sensitivity to these linguistic features.

François and Schön (2021) demonstrated that ESL learners trained in music exhibited superior prosodic awareness, with greater ability to recognize pitch variations and sentence-level stress patterns. Such enhanced prosodic sensitivity may facilitate more accurate pronunciation and fluency in spoken English, aiding ESL learners in navigating subtle shifts in meaning conveyed by intonation and stress. Bokiev and Ismail (2021) explored ESL teachers' beliefs

about using music in language instruction within a Malaysian-speaking context. Through qualitative analysis, the researchers discovered that teachers widely recognized music's benefits for vocabulary acquisition and pronunciation. Malaysian teachers reported that songs not only engaged students but also enhanced their understanding of rhythm and intonation, essential components for fluent English communication. Choi (2022) investigated how different aspects of musical engagement impacted stress perception among Cantonese speakers learning English as a second language (ESL). Choi explored whether musical ability, measured as inherent musical skills, or formal musicianship training more effectively supported English stress perception. In the study, 124 participants were tested on tasks such as English stress discrimination, English stress sequence recall, and a Musical Ear Test. The findings revealed a key distinction: while musical ability had a positive effect on English stress perception for both Cantonese and English listeners, formal musicianship training alone did not provide significant advantages for Cantonese listeners. Additionally, among all groups, Cantonese listeners consistently performed better than English listeners, suggesting a language-specific advantage in stress perception for Cantonese speakers. The study's results, therefore, support the idea that musical ability, rather than training, facilitated language-learning tasks related to stress perception,

Conclusion

By integrating findings from neuroscience, cognitive psychology, and music education, this review of literature has highlighted the significant cognitive, neural, and pedagogical connections between music training and language learning, offering evidence for how music training may help to facilitate English as a Second Language (ESL) learning. The evidence that overlapping neural regions are activated during both music and language tasks, supporting

phonemic discrimination and syntactic processing (Koelsch, 2014; Patel, 2011), suggests that music education may offer a robust foundation for addressing specific challenges faced by ESL learners, such as pronunciation difficulties and limited working memory. Structural and functional adaptations in the brain, driven by music training, enhance auditory discrimination and memory retention, particularly in younger learners who experience heightened neuroplasticity (Moreno et al., 2013). Patel's (2011) OPERA hypothesis provides a compelling framework for understanding how music training surpasses the cognitive demands of ordinary speech, fostering precision in auditory processing that benefits both musical and linguistic skills. These findings offer support for the idea that the cognitive and neural connections between music training and language processing may be beneficial for second language acquisition (Barrett et al., 202; Peretz & Zatorre, 2005; Peretz et al., 2003, 2012) and reinforce the potential of music training as a complementary approach to traditional ESL methodologies. Future research should explore further the potential impacts of music training on ESL learners, and examine how specific musical elements such as rhythm, pitch, and prosody may impact improvements in reading comprehension, oral fluency, and cross-linguistic transfer. Such potential impacts would have important implications for enhancing language acquisition in multilingual educational settings such as those found in Canadian schools.

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